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Euxoa atrorubens sp. n. from Kyrgyzstan (Lepidoptera, Noctuidae, Agrotina)

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Abstract. The diagnosis and description of a new *Euxoa* Hübner, [1821] species, *Euxoa atrorubens* sp. n., is provided. The main external and genitalia features of the new species and its closest relatives are characterised and discussed. The imagoes are illustrated on two tables with 10 figures, and the genitalia are presented on three monochromatic plates with figures of 5 males and 4 females.

Keywords: *Euxoa*, Central Asia, description, new species, taxonomy.

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Introduction

This paper represents the fifth contribution to an ongoing series devoted to the examination of the author's extensive Asian material of the genus *Euxoa* Hübner, 1821, with particular emphasis on the description of taxa new to science. The first results of the author's investigations on the genus *Euxoa* were published in Entomofauna (Gyulai 2018), providing a concise overview of the research history of this highly diverse genus, predominantly characterised by a Holarctic distribution. That study also summarised the most important contributions to the field up to that time and included the description of seven new species. Subsequent contributions further expanded these findings: the second paper (Gyulai 2024) described four additional species; the third paper (Gyulai & Varga 2024) introduced two further species; and the fourth contribution (Gyulai 2026) provided descriptions of four new taxa. The present study continues this line of research by describing a new species of Asian *Euxoa* from Kyrgyzstan.

Abbreviations for personal and institutional collections used herein include: PGM = collection of Péter Gyulai (Miskolc, Hungary); GYP = genitalia slide of Péter Gyulai; MMR = genitalia slide of Mohammad Mohdi Rabieh; VZ = genitalia slide of Zoltán Varga; m = male; f = female; HT = holotype; PT = paratype.

Description of the new species

Euxoa atrorubens sp. n. (Figs 1–4, 11, 12, 16)

Type material. Holotype: male, S. Kyrgyzstan, Alay range, Osh Region, Chong-Alay District, 2900 m, 4 km N of Kyzyl–Eshme vill., 31. vii. 2025, leg. V. Zurilina GYP 6315 deposited in coll. P. Gyulai, Miskolc, Hungary.

Paratypes. one male and one female, with the same data as the holotype (PGM); one male, Kyrgyzstan, Zaalay, Aram Kungey, 3200 m, 10–20. vii. 1994, leg. Titov, GYP 999 (PGM). Slides: GYP 999 male; GYP 6319 female.

Diagnosis. *Euxoa atrorubens* sp. n. (Figs 1–4) is similar and the most closely related to *Euxoa aneucta* Brandt, 1938, *Euxoa aneucta binaloudica* Brandt, 1941 and *Euxoa subeucta* Varga, 2014. *E. atrorubens* sp. n. can be distinguished from the three congeners by the almost concoloured reddish-brown colour of the head and thorax vestures and forewings. Of the

three, *E. aneucta binaloudica* most closely resembles the new species in both its external features and genitalia, but the new species has broader, less elongated forewings, although the wingspans are in the same intervals (30,0–36,0 mm).

Description (Figs 1–4). Wingspan 30,0–36,0 mm. Antennae filiform, in males very finely bipectinate. Vesture of the head and thorax, the ground colour of the forewings and the fringe are almost concolourous reddish–brown; marginal field slightly darker with slight greyish suffusion; fringe slightly lighter. The wing pattern is obscure. The orbicular and reniform macules are hardly discernible; the slightly lighter shade is of the ground colour, and the claviform spot is absent. The antemedial and the postmedial transversal lines are fine, dark brown, hardly visible; the subterminal line is obscure, sinuous, and lighter brown. Hindwings are whitish–pale brownish, with broad, very diffuse, slightly darker pale brownish marginal suffusion and without cellular macula; fringe whitish. The underside of the forewings whitish with light brownish suffusion, hindwings are whitish; all the wings are patternless.

The male genitalia (Figs 11, 12) are characterised by the weak and long, apically pointed uncus; the subquadrangular, high juxta, dorsally–medially with a u-shaped depression with two lateral, triangular, symmetric extensions and with a triangular ventral extension. Valvae are almost evenly elongate, but the dorsal costa is slightly enlarged; the cucullus section dorsally strongly elongated, terminated in a row of strong setae. The harpe is long and slender, slightly outwardly curved, apically rounded. The saccular processes are long, both distally finely curved outward, asymmetrically long, the left one is shorter; vinculum v-shaped. The aedeagus is strong, almost straight. The everted tube of the endophallus is recurved dorsally; the basal diverticulum is large, elliptical, prominent; the medial one is flatly recurved; the distal section of the tube of the vesica is almost evenly broad; the terminal dorsal diverticulum is absent.

In the female genitalia (Fig. 16), the ovipositor is moderately long, triangular, with papillae anales that are apically pointed. Apophyses anteriores are short, terminally spatulate; apophyses posteriores are very long, fine, about two times as long as apophyses anteriores. The antrum is broadly V-shaped. Ductus bursae is membranous, tubular, evenly broaden posteriorly, with the two laminar plates long. The appendix bursae is large and laterally strongly prominent. Corpus bursae slightly saccate, anterior part smaller, further section elongated.

Distribution. The new species is local and rare, known only from the high mountains of Kyrgyzstan in the Alay–Transalay range.

Etymology. The name of the new species originated from its reddish–brown forewings.

Taxonomic note. At the time of *E. subeucta* description, the only known specimen from Kyrgyzstan was included in the *E. subeucta* paratype series (see Varga, 2014), as forewings are slightly lighter reddish–brown than those of the newer ones and the genital differences were very small and it was not possible to know from a single specimen whether this was non–individual variability. This specimen was included as a paratype for the new species described above.

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Figures 1–8. *Euxoa* spp. adults. **1.** *E. atrorubens* sp. n., HT, m, S. Kyrgyzstan, Alay range, Osh Region, Chong–Alay District, 2900 m, 4 km N of Kyzyl–Eshme vill., 31. vii. 2025, leg. V. Zurilina GYP 6315 (PGM); **2.** *E. atrorubens* sp. n., PT, m, S. Kyrgyzstan, Alay range, Osh Region, Chong–Alay District, 2900 m, 4 km N of Kyzyl–Eshme vill., 31. vii. 2025, leg. V. Zurilina (PGM); **3.** *E. atrorubens* sp. n., PT, m, Kyrgyzstan, Zaalay, Aram Kungey, 3200 m, 10–20. vii. 1994, leg. Titov, GYP 999 (PGM); **4.** *E. atrorubens* sp. n., PT, f, S. Kyrgyzstan, Alay range, Osh Region, Chong–Alay District, 2900 m, 4 km N of Kyzyl–Eshme vill., 31. vii. 2025, leg. V. Zurilina GYP 6319 (PGM); **5.** *Euxoa aneucta* Brandt, 1938, m, Iran, prov. Kerman, Kuh–e–Kabir, 3500–3600 m, 2–5. vii. 2001, leg. S. Nykl (PGM); **6.** *Euxoa aneucta* Brandt, 1938, f, Iran, prov. Esfahan, Fereidun Shar, 2400 m, 30. vii.–1. viii. 2001, leg. S. Nykl, GYP 6326 (PGM); **7.** *E. aneucta binaloudica* Brandt, 1941, m, Iran, Khorasan Razavi, Shirhad, 3100 m, 28. viii. 2011, leg. M. M. Rabieh, MMR 285 (PGM); **8.** *E. aneucta binaloudica* Brandt, 1941, f, Iran, Binaloud Mts., 10. ix. 2012, leg. M. M. Rabieh, GYP 4602 (PGM).

Figures 9–10. *Euxoa* spp. adults and **Figures 11–13.** male genitalia. **9.** *E. subeucta* Varga, 2014, PT, m, Tajikistan, W Pamir Mts., Rushan distr., 3400 m, 1–10. viii. 2010, leg. V. Gurko, GYP 1826 (PGM); **10.** *E. subeucta* Varga, 2014, PT, f, Pakistan, Deosai Mts., near Chilim, 3400–3700 m, 15–20. viii. 2004, leg. V. Gurko, (PGM); **11.** *E. atrorubens* sp. n., HT, S. Kyrgyzstan, Alay range, Osh Region, Chong–Alay District, 2900 m, 4 km N of Kyzyl–Eshme vill., 31. vii. 2025, leg. V. Zurilina GYP 6315 (PGM); **12.** *E. atrorubens* sp. n., PT, Kyrgyzstan, Zaalay, Aram Kungey, 3200 m, 10–20. vii. 1994, leg. Titov, GYP 999 (PGM); **13.** *E. aneucta* Brandt, 1938, Iran, VZ 8250 (PGM).

Figures 14–15. male genitalia and **Figures 16–19.** female genitalia. **14.** *E. aneucta binaloudica* Brandt, 1941, Iran, Khorasan Razavi, Shirhad, 3100 m, 28. viii. 2011, leg. M. M. Rabieh, MMR 285 (PGM); **15.** *E. subeucta* Varga, 2014, PT, Tajikistan, W Pamir Mts., Rushan distr., 3400 m, 1–10. viii. 2010, leg. V. Gurko, GYP 1826 (PGM); **16.** *E. atrorubens* sp. n., PT, S. Kyrgyzstan, Alay range, Osh Region, Chong–Alay District, 2900 m, 4 km N of Kyzyl–Eshme vill., 31. vii. 2025, leg. V. Zurilina GYP 6319 (PGM); **17.** *Euxoa aneucta* Brandt, 1938, Iran, prov. Esfahan, Fereidun Shar, 2400 m, 30. vii.–1. viii. 2001, leg. S. Nykl, GYP 6326 (PGM); **18.** *E. aneucta binaloudica* Brandt, 1941, Iran, Binaloud Mts., 10. ix. 2012, leg. M. M. Rabieh, GYP 4602 (PGM); **19.** *E. subeucta* Varga, 2014, PT, Tajikistan, W Pamir Mts., Rushan distr., 3400 m, 1–10. viii. 2010, leg. V. Gurko, GYP 6323 (PGM).

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